

Repetition and recognition in YouTube narratives of Covid-19 survival

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This essay analyzes the structures of recognition underlying the reception of three video narratives telling stories of Covid-19 survivors. Published by top U.S. news networks between March and April 2020, recordings were intended to reassure the American public that the epidemic would be contained. Taking as its point of departure Priscilla Wald's work on repetitive patterns in the formula of communicable disease outbreaks, and Rita Felski's theory of recognition, it examines 832 comments associated to the videos. It argues that viewers' engagement can be assessed looking at the new meanings commenters add to the contents of the recordings, and proposes to delineate the contours of a useful theoretical framework for future research on the relationship between reassurance, recognition, and repetition in the outbreak narrative.

Keywords: recognition; repetition; reassurance; outbreak narrative; Covid-19

Introduction

In *Contagious Cultures, Carriers, and the Outbreak Narrative* (2008), Priscilla Wald investigates accounts of the worst infections in the U.S. starting with Typhoid Mary, in 1906, through most of the 20th century, until the emergence of HIV. Repetition of forms and meanings leads her to conclude that there is a narrative formula of communicable disease outbreaks. The formula combines historical and fictive material, and draws on themes from a variety of genres (such as religious narratives, tales of heroic battles and epidemiological literature) to explain the epidemic. It “fuses the transformative force of myth with the authority of science” (33) and “the heroism of afflicted individuals in the face of adversity” (217) into one main course of action. Inevitably, its plot “begins with the identification of an emerging infection, includes

discussion of the global networks throughout which it travels; and chronicles the epidemiological work that ends with its containment” (33).

The outbreak story has consequences. It shapes our “attitudes towards disease emergence” (Wald 3) and conditions our “responses [...] to a changing world” (3), affecting “survival rates and contagion routes” (3). As it circulates through the media, in novels, films and internet websites, it provides “a way to educate the public about the threat” (31), so that we are able to make sense of a new reality and develop expectations about how events should unfold. The narrative also helps create a profound sense of community, and reinforces “the social connections” (12) that catastrophic illnesses dissolve. In essence, as described by Wald in an interview conducted for *Southern Cultures* by Kym Weed on April 2, 2020, “the outbreak narrative is the narrative about fear and panic [...], but it’s also a narrative of reassurance.” Because we are familiar with the story, “because [we know that] it’s happened many times, [...] there [is] a sense of, ‘Oh well, we’ll contain it [the virus].’”

Knowing the story, however, is not enough for reassurance to be transmitted. It may happen that readers, however familiar with the formula, still do not have a sense that the virus will be contained and fear its unknown impact on their lives. It may happen that the well-known religious, heroic and/or scientific explanations of the disease that intermingle in the narrative do not soothe their pandemic panic. My point is that for the story to work as a means of hope, readers need to engage themselves with it. Something must speak to them and catch their attention, so that they feel involved in its plot. Besides recognizing the story, they must recognize themselves in it.

This is a topic that Rita Felski develops in *Uses of Literature* (2008), where she maps four modern modes of engaging with literature. The first one, recognition, entails the feeling of familiarity. She writes: “When we recognize something, we literally

‘know it again’; we make sense of what is unfamiliar by fitting it into an existing scheme, linking it to what we already know” (25). Sometimes, upon reading a “description, a constellation of events, a conversation between characters, an unknown monologue” (23):

Suddenly and without warning, a flash of connection leaps across the gap between text and reader; an affinity or an attunement is brought to light. I may be looking for such a moment, or I may stumble on it haphazardly, startled by the prescience of a certain combination of words. In either case, I feel myself addressed, summoned, called to account: I cannot help seeing traces of myself in the pages I am reading. Indisputably, something has changed; my perspective has shifted; I see something that I did not see before. (23)

In this moment of engagement with the text, readers feel that they recognize themselves in it. At once, within the same movement, they feel recognized by the narrative.

Recognition “guarantees interpellation” (34), Felski insists, meaning that individuals feel as if the written words were speaking to them and acknowledging their existence. As a result, readers get to know something new, of which they were not aware before. To emphasize this connection between new knowledge and acknowledgment, Felski relies on the concept of dialogic identity: the self arises in relation to, when it is acknowledged by another. This mode of reading thus involves an “encounter with a generalized other” (32) who calls us to affiliate with it. Through “such sparks of affiliation” (34) we reinforce our commonalities as well as our conviction of personal distinctiveness.

Crucially, Felski argues that the self is always “formed at its core through the mediating force of stories, metaphors, myths and images” (16) of others. She adds that recognition affects “our actions as well as the stories we tell about ourselves” (33). For all our personal distinctiveness, despite differences in our stories, how individual

readers experience recognition is conditioned by the cultural, social and political pressures in the environment. This allows Felski to speak of “structures of recognition” (43), or common frameworks of engagement within particular groupings. Which means that certain communities, at certain times and spaces, will recognize themselves in certain texts at the same interpellation points. The question is: how can we identify these structures of engagement with a text?

When Felski warns that “[r]ecognition is not repetition” (25), she bases her claim on the idea that to know again “denotes not just the previously known, but the becoming known” (24); that is, “the knowing more than is already familiar” (25). During the act of knowing more: “Something that may have been sensed in a vague, diffuse, or semi-conscious way now takes on a distinct shape, is amplified, heightened, or made newly visible” (25). At this point, two considerations must be made. One: that something is heightened or made visible means that it was hidden or lessened, not that it did not exist. It appears to me that the new knowledge we gain in reading a book that we think is about us has been there all the time, implicit, only that we did not consciously know about it. Two: repetition is not mere duplication. We do not repeat verbatim; every repetition carries new inflections and adds something different to the original. As Neal R. Norrick (1994) argues: “On the one hand, the repeat borrows recognizable elements from its original, but on the other hand, it differs from that original, if only through reference to it and contextual separation from it” (15). Ultimately, for Norrick, it is this separation from the original context that invests the repeat with new meanings. Of this opinion is also Michael Toolan (2016), when he asserts that we may find “new implicatures” in repetition by virtue of the “new context” where it happens (25). If this is so, and if there is an element of repetition (however semi-conscious the repeat is) in every act of recognition, when we recognize ourselves in a text we heighten the

original, making the implicit visible in our stories. In what follows I work with this concept of recognition as amplified repetition in the context of Covid-19.

Method and data

The present essay examines the structures of recognition underlying the reception of three video narratives published by the American news media, on YouTube. They contain stories of patients who survived coronavirus: “Signs of Hope as Covid-19 Survivors Return Home” (ABC News); “Recovering Coronavirus Patients Share Stories of Survival” (CBS This Morning), and “Coronavirus Survivors Speak Out About Recovery Challenges” (NBC Nightly News). Posted between March 18 and April 19, 2020, at the heights of the Covid-19 lockdown, when cases were rising in the U.S. and hospitals were flooded, the words of those who survived the disease intended to comfort the public with the hope that the microbe would be controlled. Videos were broadcast by top U.S. news networks: American Broadcasting Company, Columbia Broadcasting System, and National Broadcasting Company. Selection was based on the number of subscribers to the channels (more than 1 million), viewers (over 20,000), and comments (81 on ABC, 603 on CBS, and 726 on NBC). Videos lasted from 2’12 to 3’30 minutes. They were transcribed manually and coded using thematic analysis.

I follow William F. Owen (1984) in defining a theme as “the patterned semantic issue or locus of concern around which a [discursive] interaction centers” (274). To determine its relevance in a text, he proposes to work with the number of “explicit repeated use[s] of the same wording” as well as with recurring threads of meanings “through different wording” (275). The advantage of this method is that it allows the researcher to move beyond verbatim repetitions, and counting words and phrases, into the interpretation of implicit messages. In accordance with Owen’s method, drawing on

Wald's study of the outbreak narrative, three themes were identified: religious, heroic, and scientific.

In November 2020, the 1,410 comments¹ associated to the videos were exported to three PDF files and numbered in the order they appeared on the platform, without sorting by "Top Comments" or "Newest First." Because YouTube does not inform of exact times and days of posting, and only gives a time frame of months, I use these numbers, along with the name of the channel viewers post on, in order to reference the comments' source. Numbers are intended to provide an estimate of the location of comments on the site. As a rule, names of users are not indicated to respect their privacy and YouTube not-real name policy.² Comments that simply stated the need to share survivors' stories were discarded from analysis. They showed that commenters were grateful to the news channel for spreading positivity, but did not provide information of how viewers felt reassured by the narrative. Jokes, and outright accusations of fake news or crisis actors that did not justify the causes for their claim were taken as instances of readers' complete disengagement from the narrative. The analysis centered on a final set of 832 comments that responded to the three themes identified. Comments were edited slightly for readability purposes only.

The remainder of this essay is organized as follows. The next section describes the video narratives at hand. After which, in the following three sections, comments are analyzed. The final section draws concluding remarks. Before proceeding, it is important to clarify that I am using the term "narrative" in the dictionary sense of the word, as any account, short and long, written, oral and visual that presents "a situation or series of events," and "promotes a particular point of view or set of values." Both, videos and comments are, therefore, treated as narratives.

Covid-19 videos of reassurance

In March 2020, testimonies of corona survivors started to appear on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, websites such as < <https://covid19survivordiaries.com/>>, and YouTube. On YouTube many individuals created and uploaded their videos directly. Most videos, however, were created and uploaded by news channels.

At the time, visits to news sites within the U.S. increased by fifty-seven percent (Tracy 2020). According to Pew Research Center, in the survey conducted April 20-26, 2020, as part of the Election News Pathways Project, fifty-six percent of American adults in search of Covid-19 updates looked to the news (over health organizations' and government sites) for information (Mitchell, Oliphant, and Shearer). Of this population, seventy-one percent watched the news on social platforms, among which YouTube stood as the second most popular (23%), after Facebook (36%) (Shearer and Mitchell). Clear majorities in this group of YouTube news viewers indicated that besides looking for facts (48%), they looked for opinion and commentary on the platform (51%) (Stocking et al.).

The three video narratives under analysis are structured around mini-interviews to American survivors. Interviewees are spread over the country and represent a broad spectrum of the population in gender, age, race, class, educational and occupational background. Their nationality is emphasized in all recordings, but the nation becomes especially prominent in the ABC broadcast, where the content is introduced with the hashtag #America Strong. Either the news host or a national correspondent guides survivors through the telling of their stories with questions about "how they were treated" and "how recovery is going" (CBS). The number of interviews per video ranges from three (ABC and CBS) to four (NBC). These are grouped together in narratives that combine the voices of respondents with the voice-over of the interviewer.

The basic pattern of these narratives is circular in time, from the present to the past and back to the present. Some start with the patients quarantined at home, surrounded by their families. The presence of families (either through photographs or live) is a repeated motif, indicating positive personal relationships, character traits and quality of life. Other narratives start with the patients being wheeled out of the hospital ready to hug their loved ones. When this happens, survivors in their masks are cheered on by doctors and nurses lining along the halls, as if they were heroes and recovery was the outcome of their bravery and outstanding achievements. Significantly, this image of brave coronavirus survivors clapped by health workers circulated widely through the U.S. media at the time, prompting the perception of survival as a national feat. Which makes sense upon considering that, according to Wald, “disease outbreaks” are often imagined “as ‘foreign’ or ‘alien’ agents that posed a national threat” (27), and fighting the virus is usually cast in national terms.

Past symptoms come next. Informants focus on chest tightening, troubled breathing, confusion, and the feeling that they were going to die. Fear of death is particularly acute for those with the most complex past medical histories: Dzidra Junior and Frank Keller. Junior, a breast-cancer survivor, compares the pain and suffering of both illnesses to conclude that coronavirus is “much worse”: “Breast cancer was a breeze in comparison with this,” she says to NBC News’ Gadi Schwartz. For his part, Keller, an 87-year-old retired marine from San Diego, was in critical condition when he was evacuated from a cruise ship and taken to a hospital in Mae West, Puerto Rico. In the words of David Begnaud, for CBS: “He arrived with pneumonia and five underlying conditions, severe heart conditions, including a leaky heart valve and even emphysema in one lung.” In spite of this, he survived.

Patients go through three forms of treatment: isolation, antibiotics and oxygen. Most survivors address two recovery challenges: dizziness and fatigue. Some, like John Pratsinakis on NBC, do physical therapy at home to gain strength and mobility. It is at this moment, he says, that he sees “the light at the end of the tunnel.” Narrative endings vary according to the abilities and intentions of the tellers. If they have clinical expertise (like Dr. Arthur Zak in NBC), they manifest their resolve to return to the front lines where they contracted the virus. Occasionally, they offer to help donating plasma or giving advice on how to fight the virus through online support systems. Survivors may also express gratitude for their health to God. Such is the case of Clay Bentley, from Georgia, who on CBS relates that when he could not breathe: “All of a sudden, [he] felt the Lord [and][...] felt him blow air in [his lungs].” While Bentley admits that faith was key to his survival, Keller confesses that he “could not have done it without the hospital outstanding efforts and, finally, the grace of God” (CBS).

Videos are clearly intended as “signs of hope” (ABC), and proof that “there’s hope happening” in America (CBS). Repetition of words and phrases related to the themes of religion, heroism, and medical science suggests three triggers of hope or means of reassurance. In the first theme, survival is achieved through spirituality: by faith in God’s mercy the patient overcomes the horrors of the pandemic and stays healthy. The second theme transforms survivors from victims to heroes that fight and win over a battle with sheer courage. In the third theme, it is through the aid of doctors and hospital staff that the subject remains alive. The table below shows the themes providing reassurance to the public and the number and percentages of viewers who commented on them:

Themes providing reassurance	Responses to themes	
	N=832	%
Surviving by faith in God	388	46
Surviving by heroic courage	129	21
Surviving by scientific advances	225	27
Combination of themes	16	5

Surviving by faith

Of 832 comments analyzed, 388 respond to the theme of surviving by faith. Readers who feel interpellated by religion add details on the spiritual origin, contagion and containment of the disease. Despite differences, answers are in agreement that the virus was engineered by God as “a warning” to humanity that “we have forgotten him,” and that we need “to realize how small and weak we really are” (CBS #24). Very few perceive the virus as the work of the devil or as man-made (NBC # 260, 350, 399). When the latter is the case, Covid-19 is a punishment for the human sin of arrogance. Whichever the genesis of the microbe, the fact is that solely lack of faith caused the pandemic and is facilitating its spread.

Pleads to God for forgiveness combine with prayers to help those who test positive, and expressions of gratitude for his mercy and grace on survivors. Most frequent are calls for conversion, like this one:

This is the beginnings of sorrows as Jesus speaks of in Matthew 24: 4-8. One devastating thing after another will lead to the coming of Christ sooner or later. Jesus loves us all and died on our behalf as ransom for our sins. John 3:16. Look at what's happening in the world, it's real. Read the 4 Gospels in the Bible. Sin and corrupt ways of life put us in this predicament and Jesus is the only hope and light for our broken hearts, minds and souls [...]. Confess your sins and ask him to change your Life. (CBS #477)

References to the Bible are common. Besides the passages above, commenters quote from Psalms, Exodus and Jeremiah on plagues and pestilence. Biblical prophecy reassures participants that only fear and love of God can contain the disease, and his word is true. God is to be feared, but not the pandemic, which is taken as a sign of a second coming. Noteworthy is the emphasis, running through many comments, on the reality of Covid-19 to prove the reality of God. The argument is that just as the pandemic seems unreal but is very real, so is God. The following commenter advances the argument, drawing on the invisibility of both, God and the virus:

I made up my mind that this is the day that the Lord has made. I will rejoice and be glad in it. No weapon formed against me shall prosper. If people feared the invisible God like the invisible virus, what a better world it would be. (CBS #190)

In response to the constant summon to faith, some negative comments (17 in total) are posted. One states: "The amount of 'God' in these comments is disheartening" (CBS #118). Others accuse believers of being "god bots" (CBS #384), or claim that "[t]here is no God, God is just pretend" (CBS #532), and "God didn't help at all" (NBC #672).

Immediately, viewers answer in strong terms:

Hope is good right now. It is positive. It doesn't matter where it comes from [...]. If you are a believer and very ill and end up recovering, your only thought of course is going to be that God saved you. If you are a believer and avoid catching it, you will likely credit God for protecting you. Such is the nature of believers [...]. Live and let live. (CBS #571)

Interactions such as this show that affiliations are created among participants, and efforts are made to protect the community from outsiders who do not believe in God. Likewise, they point out a general tendency to subscribe to just one source of hope, as if themes excluded each other. It is true that some viewers mix religious with scientific and heroic terms. God, in fact, is hailed as “our mighty physician” (CBS #19), “a doctor” (CBS #98) “a miracle worker” (CBS #362), and a “shield” (ABC #38). Once the Bible is described as a “vaccine” (CBS # 539), faith as “the armour God gave you” (CBS #85), and survivors as “a mighty army of warriors” (NBC #546). That notwithstanding, the idea that “[g]oing to the hospital is for those of little faith” (CBS #220) is pervasive.

Surviving by heroic courage

The same reticence about going to the hospital is shown by viewers who identify with the heroic theme in the video narratives. Most of these viewers mention that they had the virus or know somebody close to them (family and friends) who did, and recovered on their own, without medical attention:

I tested positive for the virus and found that using the same recovery methods used for fighting bacterial pneumonia, i.e.: foods, water, green tea, fruit juices, and fever breaking actions, helped me greatly to survive the lung infection and 104 fever temperatures [...]. Hang in there and follow known recovery methods by the book, and you will make it thru without hospital care [...]. I made it (I am 61 years old) and so can you [...]. Keep clean and practice social distancing as well!!! (NBC #247)

Comparison of Covid-19 with pneumonia, bronchitis and influenza is highly frequent due to the shared symptoms of high fever, severe cough and shortness of breath. Many commenters list the short and long-term effects associated with these illnesses to highlight similarities. Hence, recommendations always are: to rest, drink plenty of water, lots of nutrients, antibiotics and vitamins. Viewers advise homemade remedies (herbal medicines, ginger tea, lemon drinks, orange juice, cold showers and inhaling the vapor of hot water steams), eating more fruits, vegetables, less meat, and working out daily as preventive measures. They also encourage social distancing, but not staying home because: “You can’t build an immunity sitting inside” (NBC #570).

The current pandemic is not due to lack of faith, but lack of healthy habits. As one commenter makes clear: “People get sick because they don’t take care of themselves” (CBS #503). That taking care of ourselves or attaining good physical condition requires “determination” (NBC #572), “strong will” (NBC #349) and “courage” (NBC #26), leads viewers in this group to draw on the old metaphor of fighting an illness like a war enemy. As one commenter puts it: “How to fight? Do you have poor Nutritional status? Add nucleotides to your diet, onions, potatoes, liver, collard greens, etc” (NBC #686).

Expressions such as: “stay strong” (NBC #84), “you will beat this tiny bug” (CBS #523), and “Let’s keep fighting America!” (CBS #313), indicate that military language is used to conceptualize the process of getting physically fit. Of interest in this regard is that the nationalistic overtones in the videos echo just faintly in sporadic comments, most notably in those addressing the first Covid-19 outbreak in China, and in posts on domestic environmental policies. In the former, the virus is not an unhealthy lifestyle but a foreign agent infiltrating America:

The virus was concocted in a lab in Wuhan China, not at the meat market. The virus was bioengineered by war purposes against the United States. If you know anybody who's died from the China virus, know they were murdered by the Chinese government and it was no accident. (NBC #627)

In the latter, war is against the government's non-ecological laws:

What was grand about America was its scale. The vastness of its forest, the richness of expansive prairies, the thriving lakes [...]. Today, gone, replaced by a never before seen landscape of endless pavement, polluted air and water [...]. Let's end the oil and coal economy, provide health care for all [...]. Go USA. (NBC #561)

All in all, Covid-19 is an "act of war" (NBC #561), while patients are potential heroes and survivors "the real superheroes of the world" (NBC #612). Not unexpectedly, comments referring to the many anonymous heroes who survived the virus without being honored are recurrent. One commenter writes: "There are literally hundreds of thousands of 'survivors' of this particular virus [...]. I have had it" (NBC #403).

Likewise, another emphasizes that: "A lot more people have had it than we think" (NBC #257). This prompts some negative reactions on the part of a small number of viewers with underlying medical conditions (cancer, obesity and HIV). For them, watching the videos generates a deep sense of being treated unfairly because what others consider heroic is just part of their daily routines:

Having experienced disability, let me tell you that no matter how good you feel after you think you have 'recovered,' the rest of the world isn't going to be cheering you on as some kind of hero. Entirely the opposite. This pandemic affected a lot of people, but welcome to the minority who have experience disability. You are marked for life [...], you are far less hireable, credit worthy, fat chance of getting just about anything you ever apply for again, outside of the rare charity case [...]. Enjoy your fifteen minutes of fame as a 'hero,' because life as you knew it is over. (NBC #360)

Surviving by scientific advances

Comments responding to the scientific theme applaud doctors, health care and scientists as the real heroes of the pandemic. They are admired for their hard work, their nobility and courage in trying to save lives risking their own. For viewers in this group, Covid-19 does not transmit through lack of faith or healthy habits, but through lack of knowledge about pathogens: “The more scientists can learn, the closer they can get to making treatments and potentially vaccines” (NBC #448).

A minority feels hopeful that the knowledge gained by the history of epidemics will help control the disease. One commenter reminds others: “We survived the plague, Influenza, Polio, Cholera, SARs, and Ebola. And we will survive CORONA” (ABC #60). Viewers also mention malaria, dengue, and H1N1 to describe how consistently pandemics repeat themselves and derive comfort from the thought that, as in the past, a cure will be discovered. A majority, however, does not feel reassured by conjectures and want more facts.

Commenters ask about infection and mortality rates, types of Covid tests, and reliable evidence on plasma donations. They offer information about the permanent effects of coronavirus on “the lining in your lungs” and “blood cells” (NBC #271), percentage of loss in lung function (ABC #66), treatment of hospitalized patients with “hydroxychloroquine” and “azithromycin” (ABC #71), and different coronavirus strains:

There are two strains of this virus, the “L” strain and the “S” strain. Just because people survived the “L” strain does not mean they are not susceptible to the “S” strain, which is the strain killing people. (CBS #476)

Some participants refer each other to YouTube interviews with coronavirus experts (NBC #542), “serological studies” (NBC #614), research cases conducted with Covid patients, and publications by Oxford and Harvard on preliminary cures (NBC #558). As

indicated by the vocabulary used and the data brought to the fore, viewers are aware of the (popular) science surrounding Covid, and it is precisely this knowledge that prevents them from fully engaging with the contents of the video narratives, which are considered to be inconsistent, insufficient and misleading. For instance, this individual finds suspicious that survivors do not quarantine from family members: “How is it that these people are with their families and are NOT passing it to their kids or spouses?? Very suspicious” (CBS #516). The following commenter wonders about the masks survivors wear in the videos: “I see so many people wearing the plain thin masks when the news media says they are not effective. Can anyone explain that to me?” (CBS #80). Others ask about the possibility that a person, once recovered, becomes infected again: “Can a person who’s once infected with the virus and recover, get infected again? I’ve never been able to find this answer. No thoughts, feelings and opinions, please, I am just looking for the answer” (CBS #388).

Sometimes, commenters are “just curious how the antibiotics [that survivors in the videos] were given helped them when this is a viral infection” (CBS #196). Basically, disengagement arises from the fact that Covid is decontextualized and stripped of its specific uniqueness: “There is no context for this video,” says one comment associated to the NBC recording (#569). The post below is more vehement:

I would appreciate it if NBC [...] would stop spreading misinformation and confusion, and actually educate the people about the viruses and how they work, instead of spitting out ALL the misinformation that is causing fear and confusion. It is a deliberate attack on the minds and hearts of the people, and violates the spirit of the policies that I have seen these news organizations claim to support. Those claims were proven to be lies when textbook examples of propaganda and filibuster are being broadcast to manipulate the minds of the people who cannot think beyond the next day or next week. (NBC #684)

Accusations of misinformation and confusion not always shade into propaganda and filibustering. Even when they do, as in the above, the media is charged with intentionally deceiving the population about the specific circumstances of the virus, not about its existence. For these viewers, Covid is not a lie, but the spread of lies contributes to the spread of the virus, whose control depends on the effective communication of verifiable facts by the news, as much as on the ability of the public to think and discern what is true or false. Since none of these options seems particularly possible for these commenters, they end up disseminating the same fear they speak against:

There won't be a vaccine for a long time because we're in the first wave and a virus has 3/4 waves. So, what makes you believe that this is over? [...]. So, stop believing a lie [...]. A study found that people once positive, then negative, tested positive again. It's just a false sense of hope. (NBC #539)

Conclusion

Using a thematic mode of interpretation, this essay examines patterns of recognition in 832 comments associated to three YouTube videos of Covid-19 survivors. In the understanding that recognition is amplified repetition, it studies the meanings readers add to the contents of the recordings to assess their engagement with what they are told. Following upon Wald, three themes are identified.

Out of 388 viewers that responded to the first theme of surviving by faith, ninety-six percent were confident that belief in God would save them from the disease. They recognized the religious vocabulary in the video narratives and added to it drawing on their theological knowledge. With the assistance of the Bible and its prophecies, they made sense of the unfamiliar Covid-19 situation and called others to convert.

Out of 129 viewers that responded to the second theme, surviving by heroic courage, a majority were confident that fighting for health with good food and exercise would get them through the pandemic. The image of survivors cheered by hospital staff as heroes conjured in these commenters past feelings of being sick with the flu, running a fever, experiences of recovery through homemade remedies, and thoughts that disease was a war within them.

Most of 225 respondents to the third theme, surviving by scientific advances, disengaged from the recordings at the points where medical symptoms, treatment and recovery challenges were described. These viewers recognized the chronicle of the “epidemiological work that ends with [the] containment” of the virus (Wald 33) in the video narrative, and expanded on it with factual details of the coronavirus. Yet, the contradictions and inconsistencies they found in the recordings indicated that for these commenters the context of Covid-19 was so unique that hardly any sense could be made of the new microbe by linking it to what was already known about other pathogens. In the logic that we cannot know again what never happened, recognition in this latter case was, at best, partial.

In March and April 2020, when hardly anything was known about the virus, individuals derived less reassurance from the scientific suppositions and opinions circulating then, than from their own efforts of will to achieve either health or faith. It appears that in non-fictional texts, like the ones at hand, audiences feel interpellated by what they perceive to be more real (less illusory or fictional) at the time. What is clear is that the reality of everyday lives under Covid-19 conditioned the attachments of viewers to the sources that encouraged hope and that, on the basis of those attachments, communities were created. Analysis of comments indicated that very few viewers cast hope in national terms. Some mentioned relatives who were or are sick, but the sense of

kinship generated on YouTube revolved around different versions of hope. That religious, heroic and scientific hope were considered contradictory and mutually exclusionary was due to the new implicatures viewers found in repetition.

Data show that by way of the stories shared, supportive responses, pieces of advice, recommendations and repetitions of each others' words, viewers recognized themselves in the comments of others and reciprocated their recognition. More research needs to be conducted on the effects of recognition on our actions, "survival rates and contagion routes" (Wald 3). Obviously, in order to delineate the contours and evolution of these patterns of recognition and reciprocity within the current Covid-19 situation, it would be necessary to look at a more extensive corpus. Yet, in spite of its limited scope, my study may provide a useful theoretical framework for future research on the relationship between reassurance, recognition, and repetition in outbreak narratives.

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1. A total of 3,819 comments were published, but replies to comments (2,409) were excluded from analysis because their content was considered peripheral.
 2. YouTube does not force on commenters real-name restrictions and, so, many users adopt fanciful names to disguise their identity.

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